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Giuseppe Dari-Mattiacci

Marco Fabbri

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How Institutions Shape Morality*

Giuseppe Dari-Mattiacci[†] and Marco Fabbri[‡]

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Abstract

We present the results of a randomized controlled trial on the effect of the introduction of formalized property rights on individuals' moral judgments and, in particular, on utilitarian morality. We show that institutions shape morality: being exposed to private property institutions makes individuals *more* utilitarian when confronted with moral dilemmas. Our result sheds light on a possible factor contributing to the variation of moral judgments across the globe and its geographical patterns, and has implications for the consequences of major institutional reforms — both intended, such as land-titling programs, and unintended, such as the fall of

*The experiment was approved by the Research Ethics Committee Parc de Salut MAR - Barcelona, reference nr. 2018/8015/I. Participants provided informed consent. The empirical strategy was pre-specified in a pre-analysis plan that was registered at the AEA RCT Registry—ID AEARCTR-0005325—before we collected the data, and included specification of the hypothesis to be tested and of the regression approach. We are indebted to Deo-Gracias Houndolo for his support during the fieldwork, and to Dr. Charles Ibikounle who provided detailed information on the protection of land in Benin. Ametonou Charmelle, Dossou Fiogbe, Gaston Gnonlonfoun, Issifou Gounou, Colin Henderson, Madeline Holbrook, Nice Hounbagnon, Dorothee Lokossou, Aissath Salifou, Mohamed Sedou, Aparna Sundaram, and Israëlia Zannou provided excellent research assistance. We would also like to thank Ben Depoorter, John Donohue, David Enoch, Alon Harel, Keith Hollenberg, Adi Leibovitch, Michael Meurer, Mitch Polinsky, Amber Polk, Chris Robertson, Doron Teichman, Donald Wittman, Kathy Zeiler, and participants in the Law, Economics and Empirical Studies Workshop at Hebrew University of Jerusalem, the Stanford Law and Economics Seminar, and the Law and Economics Seminar at Boston University School of Law. The usual disclaimer applies. Marco Fabbri acknowledges financial support from the Marie Curie Research Grants scheme, grant H2020-MSCA-IF-2017-789596. Giuseppe Dari-Mattiacci gratefully acknowledges research support from Columbia Law School. The authors declare no competing interests.

[†]*Corresponding author.* University of Amsterdam. E-mail address: gdarimat@uva.nl.

[‡]University Pompeu Fabra & Barcelona GSE & Amsterdam Center for Law and Economics.

13 communism — on moral attitudes. A conjectural channel through which property
14 affects moral judgments is the loosening of social ties.

15 *JEL codes:* K11, O13, Z10, Z13.

16 *Keywords:* property, utilitarianism, trolley problem, morality, moral machine.

17 **1 Introduction**

18 The car you are driving has sudden brake failure and you have only two options. If you
19 go straight, the car will drive through a pedestrian crossing ahead, which will result in
20 the death of 2 men. If you swerve, the car will drive through a pedestrian crossing in the
21 other lane, which will result in the death of 1 man.¹ What would you do? Is saving two
22 worth the intentional killing of one?

23 Normative institutional analysis is often predicated on the premise that there are
24 universal moral principles, such as those derived from deontology, as in Rawls (1971), or
25 utilitarianism, as in Singer (2011). In contrast, recent empirical research in psychology
26 and anthropology shows that moral judgments vary over time and space, and are socially
27 functional (Haidt, 2007).² To sharply characterize moral dilemmas, philosophers have
28 been extensively using trolley problems in thought experiments since the late sixties (Foot,
29 1967).³ Their use has now become commonplace also in empirical research (Christensen
30 and Gomila, 2012, Greene, 2016), and the hypothetical above is one of them.

31 Individuals in different societies tend to give markedly different answers when con-
32 fronted with moral dilemmas. In the most comprehensive survey so far — the *Moral*
33 *Machine* experiment — Awad et al. (2018) collected 40 million decisions from individu-
34 als who were exposed to self-driving-car versions of the dilemma above in 233 different
35 societies. They document both geographical variation and correlation with country-level
36 cultural and institutional indicators. In particular, subjects living in countries with in-
37 dividualistic cultures tend to be more willing to accept utilitarian sacrifice, that is, to

¹Hypothetical adapted from vignettes in www.moralmachine.net. See below for more details.

²See also Abarbanell and Hauser (2010) (studying moral dilemmas in a rural Mayan societies and showing differences with respect to what is typically observed in other societies), Haidt and Graham (2007) (arguing that there are five distinct psychological systems shaping an individual's emotional reaction to five distinct sets of issues — harm/care, fairness/reciprocity, ingroup/loyalty, authority/respect, and purity/sanctity — which in turn can be seen as determinants of the world's diverse moral landscape), and Enke (2020) (providing evidence of a demand (by voters) and supply (by politicians) of different moral principles, which in turn shaped support for the various candidates in recent US presidential elections). See also more generally on the global variation in behavioral patterns Henrich et al. (2001, 2005).

³See also Thomson (1976, 1984), Kamm (1989), Unger (1996).

38 swerve in order to spare more lives while intentionally sacrificing some. What explains
39 these patterns? A plausible hypothesis is that, among other factors, legal and economic
40 institutions affect individuals' social environment and hence shape their moral judgments.
41 That is, institutions shape morality.

42 The notion that morals and, more generally, preferences and culture are endogenous to
43 the institutional setup of society has long been discussed in philosophy (Foucault, 1995),
44 sociology (Elias, 2000), history (Weber, 1976), and economics (Bowles, 1998, Tabellini,
45 2008a,b, Bisin and Verdier, 2011). More recently, empirical analyses and historical case-
46 studies have uncovered the long-term causal effect of institutions on culture (Lowe et al.,
47 2017, Greif and Tabellini, 2017, Enke, 2019, Schulz et al., 2019, Becker et al., 2020,
48 Henrich, 2020). While these studies span generations, in this paper we assess the short-
49 term effect of a discontinuous institutional change on moral judgments. In particular, we
50 focus on the effect of private property — one of the most fundamental institutions or,
51 possibly, the most fundamental institution of western societies — on utilitarianism.

52 Private property, especially of land, has been a feature of western legal cultures since
53 antiquity. It was embedded in the legal systems that shaped western law—Roman and
54 canon law—and was central to the thinking of philosophers from Plato, to Thomas
55 Aquinas, John Locke, Thomas Hobbes and Adam Smith (Garnsey, 2014). Over the past
56 several decades, the West has sought to export law and institutions supporting private
57 property of land to developing countries through a series of reforms. The question as to
58 the acceptability of utilitarian sacrifice occupies a similarly prominent role in the West's
59 moral tradition, as it reveals the tension between the maximization of aggregate welfare
60 — as proposed by utilitarians, such as Bentham (1907), Mill (1863) and Singer (2011)
61 — and the relevance of deontological constraints to the admissible means to pursue that
62 goal — as emphasized by utilitarianism's critics, among whom Rawls (1971) and John
63 Paul II (1995). In addition, the extent to which one should embrace the utilitarian cal-
64 culus has been comprehensively discussed in and is a fundamental issue behind welfarist
65 analyses of laws and institutions, and the disputation about the compatibility of welfare
66 maximization with notions of fairness (see Posner, 1979, Kaplow and Shavell, 2001, and
67 the extensive debate that followed).

68 While the relationship between private property and morality is not new to economics
69 (see, for instance, Bowles, 1998),⁴ assessing empirically its causal effects is challenging

⁴There is a large literature in legal scholarship about how morality (or, more generally, culture) shapes or should shape the law, in general, and property law, in particular (see, for instance, Merrill and Smith, 2007, Dagan and Dorfman, 2016, Zhang, 2016), we focus on the reverse question: how property shapes morality.

70 because experiments on the introduction of private property are hard to come by. This
71 limitation applies more generally to studies on the effects of institutional changes on
72 culture and, indeed, the extant literature mostly relies on geographical or historical dis-
73 continuities (Lowe et al., 2017, Schulz et al., 2019).⁵ In contrast, we present the results
74 of a study that bases identification on a randomized controlled trial.

75 To sidestep the difficulties inherent in the randomized introduction of private prop-
76 erty, we took advantage of the first case in which a property-rights reform was in fact
77 implemented as a randomized control-trial (RCT) in a pool of rural villages in the Re-
78 public of Benin. The reform, known as *Plan Foncier Rural*, consisted in the formalization
79 of previously customary land rights and was implemented in 2010-2011. In the winter
80 of 2020, we presented individuals in treated and control villages with a series of moral
81 dilemmas derived from the *Moral Machine* experiment.

82 In our primary vignette, analogous to the one presented above, each individual was
83 asked whether he or she would do nothing and, consequently, continue straight and kill
84 2 individuals, as opposed to swerving and killing only 1. In order to save 2 lives, the
85 individual had to take action, which resulted inevitably in the death of a passerby. This
86 setup captures the “negative” side of utilitarianism, that is, the acceptability of harm
87 visited upon innocents — which is commonly referred to as “utilitarian sacrifice” —
88 along the path of producing a (greater) good (Kahane et al., 2018).⁶ In a subsequent
89 vignette, the choice was between going straight and killing 1 man versus swerving and
90 killing 2 women. In this case, the utilitarian choice was to continue straight. While
91 the former scenario stacks utilitarianism against preferences for inaction, in the latter
92 scenario utilitarianism is contrasted with gender preferences.⁷

93 Our results show that, after only 9 years of exposure to the new property rights regime,
94 villagers are significantly more likely to resolve the moral dilemma in a utilitarian way,
95 that is, to kill 1 rather than 2 individuals. The estimated effects suggest that, on average,

⁵See Alesina and Giuliano (2015) for a review of the literature. There is a large literature — including randomized controlled trials — on the effect of market participation on preferences (Jha and Shayo, 2019, Margalit and Shayo, 2020) and morality (Falk and Szech, 2013). We focus on the effects of legal institution rather than market participation.

⁶Globally, individuals tend to prefer inaction to action (Awad et al., 2018). There is also an alternative notion of positive versus negative utilitarianism, which refers to the maximization of benefits versus the minimization of harms (Smart, 1958). This formulation is orthogonal to our discussion.

⁷Awad et al. (2018) report a large cross-cultural variance in moral preferences concerning gender. In our data, we found that about 1/4 of the subjects have a preference for sparing a man that is stronger than their preference for inaction; that is, they would rather swerve and spare 1 man than continue straight and spare 1 woman (Vignette 3 in Figure 1c, discussed below in the text). As explained below, in the analysis we control for individual gender preferences.

96 participants in treated villages choose to spare more lives 7% to 10% more often than
97 those in the control sample. Further analysis shows that the observed effect is driven by
98 participants who were in a position to actually benefit from the reform, that is, those
99 who hold land parcels in the treated area and have higher income levels, stronger market
100 integration, or shorter travel distance from state tribunals. Since having the logistical
101 and financial means to access formal courts is a *de facto* prerequisite to take advantage of
102 the documentary evidence provided by the reform in adverse land claims, these findings
103 reinforce the result that formal property rights affect moral values.⁸

104 In the closest study to ours, Di Tella et al. (2007) find that providing formal land
105 titles to a group of squatters in the outskirts of Buenos Aires had a positive effect on
106 individualism — that is, the belief that one can be successful irrespective of the support
107 of a group — and other beliefs associated with a capitalist mindset, such as the role
108 of markets, money and merit. In contrast, we directly test the effect of the reform on
109 utilitarianism. Although different, our findings are related and largely consistent with
110 theirs as individualism correlates positively both with utilitarianism (Awad et al., 2018)
111 and with the strength of property rights (Lehavi and Licht, 2011, Dari-Mattiacci and
112 Guerriero, 2015) in cross-country studies.⁹

113 These associations suggest that a possible channel through which private property
114 affects utilitarianism is the loosening of pre-existing social ties. Customary rights are
115 enforced through recourse to traditional local authorities and hence enforcement is deeply
116 embedded in social relations. Under these circumstances it is crucial for an individual
117 not to exhibit behaviors that may alienate social connections and consequently weaken

⁸In a contribution based on data collected in 2016-2017 across Beninese villages, Fabbri (2020b) combines an institutional and legal analysis of the Beninese PFR with survey questions and experimental games to show that the reform increased cooperation and trust choices in social dilemmas, but only for those individuals who face relatively low costs to conduct a legal action. In particular, the author shows that the absence of paved roads and difficulties to reach state tribunals magnify the cost of a legal dispute and jeopardize the use of formal courts. The same inverse relationship between the accessibility of state legal institutions and pro-social behavior is reported in Fabbri and Dari-Mattiacci (2020). The authors conduct a modified Dictator game experiment in Beninese rural villages and show that individuals who were awarded private property through the PFR are less likely to steal from peers' endowment, albeit the effects progressively fade away when distance from roads increases.

⁹While Di Tella et al. (2007) assess the effect of “becoming an owner” for a specific group of individuals in a society where property rights are already formalized, we study a formalization of property rights affecting the entire local society, including both those who enjoyed customary property rights prior to the reform and those who did not. While the squatters were given a land title, the reform we consider did not directly redistribute land; in contrast, it primarily concerned the formalization and recording of land titles. (In addition, the formalization occurred after clearing possible disputes as to existing entitlements.). Lastly, their study is based on a quasi-natural experiment — namely, the fact that some owners disputed the re-allocation of property rights in court while others did not — while our design is grounded in a RCT design that randomized the formalization of property rights.

118 the individuals' social standing with possibly negative repercussions on the security of
119 his or her rights. Utilitarian moral attitudes can be potentially damaging to one's social
120 embeddedness, because the willingness to break with deontological principles may be
121 interpreted as a signal of lack of trustworthiness by group members (Awad et al., 2020).
122 The more an individual's success rests on the social support he or she can gather among
123 the local community, the more costly it is to practice utilitarianism. In contrast, formal
124 property rights that are enforced by an impersonal judiciary and mainly transferred
125 through trade make social ties relatively less important and facilitate utilitarian attitudes
126 (Bowles, 1998, 91-93).

127 In sum, the introduction of formalized property rights that are upheld by a formal
128 court frees (to some extent) the individual from the need to resort to his or her social
129 relations in order to protect his or her legal rights and economic interests. In turn, this
130 makes the individual less dependent on the stability of social connections and the exhibit-
131 ing of possibly socially inappropriate moral judgments less costly. Although conjectural,
132 this interpretation is consistent with our finding that those with effective access to justice
133 in formal courts update their moral positions more strongly in response to being awarded
134 property, with the fact that in public goods experiments participants experiencing the
135 Beninese PFR increase contribution for joint projects with strangers outside the village
136 community (Fabbri, 2020a), and with the literature emphasizing the relationship between
137 kin structures, morality and institutions (Ellickson, 1991, Bernstein, 1992, Greif, 1994,
138 André and Platteau, 1998, Bowles, 1998, Henrich et al., 2005, Schulz et al., 2019, Enke,
139 2019).

140 The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. In Section 2, we describe the
141 institutional framework and present the details of the *Plan Foncier Rural*. In Section 3, we
142 discuss our identification strategy, the vignette study, and the data collection procedures.
143 Section 3.4 states the main hypothesis and the empirical specification for testing it. In
144 Section 4, we present our results. In Section 5, we offer a discussion of our findings and
145 their implications, and in Section 6, we conclude with some ideas for future research.

146 **2 Institutional Framework**

147 In recent years, systems of formal land ownership registration have been introduced in
148 nearly every African state. Nonetheless, customary land rights still represent the predom-
149 inant land-tenure arrangement in most rural areas of the African continent. Customary
150 land rights are characterized by a complex set of tenure principles and regulatory mech-

151 anisms, usually defined at the village or local level. While a variety of diverse customary
152 arrangements exists, it is possible to identify a set of common features (Delville et al.,
153 2000). Customary rights consist of socially determined land-use rules, where access to
154 land is an integral part of the social structure and tenure is determined by sociopolitical
155 relationships. Governance and enforcement of principles characterizing this system are
156 implemented by local customary authorities. The distribution of land rights is based on
157 the sociopolitical local structure and on family relationships.

158 This system implies that rights held by individuals are the result of a social and polit-
159 ical process of negotiations arbitrated by customary local authorities. This enforcement
160 process has an inherently procedural nature. Rules governing customary arrangements
161 do not provide a precise codification of each landholder's rights. Instead they only state
162 procedures by which an individual obtains access to the land. Therefore, the informal
163 nature of customary rules might be an obstacle to the establishment of secure and well-
164 defined land-property rights. Population growth and the consequent increasing pressure
165 on natural resources create serious concerns for the functioning of informal customary
166 arrangements. Scholars have noticed that the absence of written documentation regard-
167 ing land use gave rise to increasing conflicts over inheritance and disputes over land use
168 (Deininger and Castagnini, 2006).

169 In Benin, the policy response to problems due to tenure insecurity has been a land-
170 tenure reform known as the *Plan Foncier Rural* (PFR, henceforth). The reform consists
171 of socio-land surveys at the village level to identify right-holders, their rights, and parcel
172 boundaries. Rights and associated right-holders are then recorded in public registries,
173 and a process of land demarcation takes place. The process allows for public objection to
174 the proposed registration of rights and requires that right-holders and neighbors publicly
175 sign survey records (Hounkpodote, 2007).

176 According to the PFR roadmap, following the processes of land demarcation and pub-
177 lic registry recording, each local administration will then create a public land registry.¹⁰

¹⁰In the original formulation as stated in the Rural Land Act 2007-003, the local administration would also issue the "Certificat Foncier Rural", that is, land certificates that required registration to assign land ownership titles ("Titre Foncier"). Remarkably, in the original formulation of the PFR once the land-demarcation intervention and the recording of rights in a public registry have taken place, the subsequent process of releasing land certificates is purely administrative and does not require further action by landholders. The release of land certificates was de facto interrupted with the enactment of the new Rural Land Law 2013-01 creates a unique ownership document, the "Certificat de Propriete Foncier", that reunifies land certificates and ownership titles. However, as clarified also by Benin State Law 2017-15, even in cases when the local administration has not yet released the certificates, the recorded rights that constitute the basis for the land-demarcation process assign to right-holders the use of rights recognized by courts.

178 Given these characteristics, the PFR reform in Benin brought about a major change in
179 the institutional contours of ownership over land by creating a system akin to formalized
180 property rights (Fabbri and Dari-Mattiacci, 2020).

181 **3 Research Design**

182 The empirical strategy was pre-specified in a pre-analysis plan that was registered at the
183 American Economic Association’s Registry for Randomized Controlled Trials before we
184 collected the data. The pre-analysis plan included the specification of the hypothesis to
185 be tested, the regression approach, and the dimensions to be studied in the heterogeneity
186 analysis.¹¹

187 **3.1 The moral dilemmas**

188 To capture utilitarianism in moral judgments we used a series of vignettes that were
189 produced using the *Design* function on www.moralmachine.net (Awad et al., 2018). The
190 vignettes presented subjects with moral dilemmas consisting of a binary choice between
191 inaction and action, both of which resulted in the death of one or more individuals with
192 varying characteristics. Each vignette presented the heading “The car in the pictures
193 below has sudden brake failure: What would you do if you were driving the car? Choose
194 one of the two options below”, followed by two graphic representations of the two options
195 available: *Continue straight* — “In this case the car will drive through a pedestrian
196 crossing ahead, which will result in the death of: ...” — or *Swerve* — “In this case the
197 car will drive through a pedestrian crossing in the other lane, which will result in the
198 death of: ...”.

199 Our measure of utilitarianism in moral preferences is based on 2 vignettes constructed
200 by varying the number and characteristics of the individuals put on either path before
201 the car. In Vignette 1 — depicted in Figure 1a — the choice was between 2 men (if
202 *Continue straight* was chosen) and 1 man (if *Swerve* was chosen). Given that individuals
203 tend to attach greater moral weight to action (but see also Abarbanell and Hauser, 2010),
204 choosing to act has a moral cost for the individual, which is greater the greater the weight
205 given to deontological constraints. Therefore, individuals who choose the *Swerve* option
206 are those with relatively weak moral constraints along the path towards a greater good,
207 that is, they are utilitarian (Kahane et al., 2018).

¹¹See AEA RCT Registry–ID AEARCTR-0005325.

The car in the pictures below has sudden brake failure: What would you do if you were driving the car?
Choose one of the two options below.

(a) Vignette 1: two men vs. one man

(b) Vignette 2: one man vs. two women

(c) Vignette 3: one man vs. one woman

Figure 1: The vignettes used in the study

208 The utilitarian dilemma presented in Vignette 2 (Figure 1b) depicts the choice between
 209 1 man (if *Continue straight* was chosen) and 2 women (if *Swerve* was chosen). In this
 210 case, the utilitarian thing to do is not to act. However, there is evidence that in some
 211 cultures subjects have gender preferences for sparing a man (Awad et al., 2018). In this
 212 case, the utilitarian choice of swerving would be confronted with a moral cost related to
 213 gender preferences. To identify the portion of utilitarian individuals in the population,
 214 we combined the answers to vignettes 1 and 2 by classifying an individual as utilitarian
 215 only if he or she had chosen to spare 2 individuals in both cases, and as non-utilitarian
 216 otherwise.

217 As we specified in the pre-analysis plan, in the analysis we also account for the indi-

218 vidual propensity to spare men versus women displayed by different participants in our
219 sample. We assessed the extent of these preferences in Vignette 3 (Figure 1c, which staked
220 1 man against 1 woman) and we used this measure as a control in the regression analysis.
221 The idea behind introducing the (pre-registered) control for gender preferences is that it
222 captures whether an hypothetical decision to swerve in Vignette 2 (i.e. sparing 1 man vs.
223 2 women) was only due to utilitarian motives or whether it was additionally influenced
224 by gender consideration (the analysis presented in section 4 shows that excluding this
225 control has no effects on the results).¹²

226 **3.2 Identification Strategy and Data Collection Procedures**

227 Due to a lack of resources, the Beninese PFR remained on paper until the Millennium
228 Challenge Corporation (MCC) subsidized an implementation program completed between
229 2010-2011. In agreement with the World Bank that designed and carried on the impact
230 evaluation of the reform, the implementation followed a RCT process involving hundreds
231 of rural villages. In fact, this is the first case of a large-scale land-tenure reform imple-
232 mented in this manner (Goldstein et al., 2018).

233 In the preliminary phase of the project, rural villages were informed of the possibility
234 to have the reform implemented and invited to apply for being included in the RCT pool.
235 As a second step, each application was examined to verify whether the village fit certain
236 eligibility criteria.¹³ A total of 576 eligible villages were included in the RCT. Once this
237 pool of villages was identified, a subsample of 300 of them was selected via public lottery,
238 and in these villages the PFR was implemented. The villages that were not selected for
239 the PFR did not receive any intervention and, as of today, continue to have customary
240 land rights. Figure 2 shows a map of the communes and villages where the reform took
241 place.

242 Our research design is based on the RCT implementation of the reform. From the
243 list of all villages in two regions that were included in the PFR lottery pool, we ran-
244 domly selected 32 villages where we performed the data collection from a sample of 576

¹²In addition to the three vignettes just discussed, during the data collection participants were pre-
sented with 6 other vignettes presenting different moral dilemmas in the form of *Continue straight* versus
Swerve. These additional vignettes – depicted in Figures 5 to 10 in Appendix B – were used to introduce
an interval between the display of each of the three vignettes described in the main text (in the sequence
of the nine vignettes in the survey, Vignette 1 was always presented as first, Vignette 2 as eighth, and
Vignette 3 as fifth) and to collect additional data we will use in a separate project.

¹³The criteria for eligibility were poverty index, potential for commercial activities, regional market
integration, local interest in promoting gender equality, infrastructure for economic activities, adherence
to the PFR application procedure, the incidence of land conflicts, and the production of main crops.

245 participants. For our identification strategy to work, some caveats are in order. First,
246 it is required that there were no pre-treatment differences in moral preferences between
247 treatment groups and that our selection of participants resulted in a balanced sample. We
248 do not have pre-treatment data for treated and control villages included in our sample.
249 This is a limitation of our study. Nonetheless, we believe that our design still provides a
250 credible identification strategy to the extent that we can argue that the implementation
251 of the reform was based on a random selection of treated villages within the lottery pool
252 and that, when analyzing data from our sample of participants, we additionally perform
253 the robustness checks described below.

254 With respect to the RCT implementation of the reform across Beninese villages, a
255 thorough impact evaluation of the reform carried on by the World Bank reports evidence
256 that the randomization determined by the lottery was successful (Omondi, 2019). In
257 particular, the World Bank team made use of both a rich set of pre- and post-treatment
258 survey data collected by a national agency, as well as of administrative monitoring and
259 evaluation data independently collected by the MCC-Benin. The impact evaluation, re-
260 sulting from a cross-evaluation performed by using these independently collected data
261 sources, show pre-intervention balance on outcome variables between treatment groups
262 and dispels residual concerns regarding the randomization performed by the lottery se-
263 lection (Goldstein et al., 2016, Omondi, 2019).

264 Concerning our sample of participants, we collected data from residents of 32 villages
265 randomly selected among those in the RCT pool. In Table 3 in Appendix A, we report
266 descriptive statistics relative to 20 socio-demographic characteristics for the subjects who
267 took part into the vignette survey. Participants in the treated group are on average older
268 (40 vs. 36.8), more likely to be married (89% vs. 83%) and to have running water at
269 home (26% vs. 18%), and show a marginally significantly higher literacy rate (40% vs.
270 33%) than those in the control group. Notwithstanding that the sample is balanced on
271 the remaining indicators – including income, acres of land owned, and seven other proxies
272 for household’s wealth – these individual characteristics might be positive associated with
273 affluence and the imbalance might signal that affluent individuals are over-represented
274 among treated.

275 We summarize here, and we the details will be reported in the next section, the
276 strategies we adopted to reduce concerns that the results we estimated are biased by
277 affluent individuals self-selecting into the treated group. First, we show that in our sample
278 the variables age, marital status, and having running water (and also, more generally,
279 income levels) are *not* associated with a larger likelihood to engage in utilitarian choices.

Figure 2: *Left Panel:* The mechanism for selecting treated villages. *Right Panel:* Distribution of treated and control villages after the RCT implementation. The green square identifies the provinces where the data collection took place.

280 Second, we employ a Lasso post-double-selection methodology (Belloni et al., 2014) for
 281 appropriately selecting the controls to be included in the regression when accidental
 282 imbalances in the sample occurs, so to improve the robustness of our causal inference
 283 (Chernozhukov et al., 2018). Finally, we also perform an heterogeneity analysis comparing
 284 categories of participants with the same income levels across treatment groups in which we
 285 show that, among equally-wealthy individuals, the treatment effects on moral preferences
 286 are concentrated on those who were affected the most by the reform.

287 Furthermore, to dispel concerns regarding self-selection, it is also necessary to show
 288 that subjects have not migrated into treated villages following the PFR randomization.
 289 As explained in the next section, we have verified that migrating out of the village of
 290 origin is rare for participants in our sample and that migration flows are similar across
 291 treatment branches.

292 3.3 Data Collection Procedures

293 Survey participants were recruited during fieldwork sessions in Beninese rural villages. A
 294 team of research assistants visited 32 villages that have been randomly selected among

295 the list of villages included in the PFR for the regions of Couffou and Mono (in the South
296 of the country) and Alibori and Borgou (in the North). The day before the experiment a
297 research assistant visited the village and requested voluntary participation in the research
298 study to the local population. Among the villagers who showed up at the convened time,
299 we randomly recruited 18 households (9 males and 9 females, older than 18 years old, and
300 maximum one participant per household) for each village, for a total of 576 participants.
301 Non-selected individuals were paid a show-up fee equal to XOF 500 (approximately \$0,85)
302 and were requested to leave.

303 Each of the 18 participants received a flat participation fee equal to XOF 500 for
304 taking part to the study. The participants took part in the vignette survey to elicit
305 moral decisions described above, in a post-experimental survey, and in other tasks not
306 related to this project. In addition, we collected participants' incentivized measure of risk
307 preferences and socio-demographic information regarding: age, gender, religion, marital
308 status, number of family members, participation to household finance management, liter-
309 acy, village of birth, years of residence in the village, income, and nine additional proxies
310 for individual wealth.¹⁴

311 **3.4 Main hypothesis and empirical specification**

312 The main hypothesis tests whether the introduction of formal property rights determined
313 a shift toward utilitarian moral attitudes. This in turn implies a preference for choosing
314 the option that results in sparing the larger number of lives. Therefore, we hypothesize
315 that, in the decisions presented in the appendix:

- 316 • In Vignette 1 (Figure 1a), villagers who experienced the reform will spare more
317 often the 2 men than participants in control villages
- 318 • In Vignette 2 (Figure 1b), villagers who experienced the reform will spare more
319 often the 2 women than participants in control villages

320 **Hypothesis 1** *The land rights reform produces more utilitarian moral preferences.*

321 To test the hypothesis, we construct the dummy variable *utilitarian*, which takes the
322 value 1 if an individual chooses to spare more lives in the two situations just described,

¹⁴Specifically: hectares of land owned, whether the house has cement floor, whether the household possess either a radio or a television, a motorbike or car, whether in the household somebody holds a bank account or a credit card, whether the house has electricity, whether the house has running water, self-reported rank of socio-economic status within the village.

323 and zero otherwise. We then apply a one-sided z test and a Chi-squared test¹⁵ comparing
324 participants in the treated and control samples and a regression analysis that controls
325 for a set of pre-specified socio-demographic characteristics. Specifically, we use a Logit
326 regression model implementing the following specification:

$$utilitarian_i = \alpha + \delta_T T_i + \mathbf{x}_i + \epsilon_i \quad (1)$$

327 where T_i is a dummy equal to 1 for subjects in treated villages, and \mathbf{x}_i is a vector
328 the individual characteristics specified in the post-experimental survey. As specified in
329 the pre-analysis plan and motivated in section 3.1, we also insert as a control a dummy
330 regarding the outcome of the decision in Vignette 3 (Figure 1c), which identifies those
331 individuals who take a positive action in order to swerve and spare 1 man instead of 1
332 woman (in the analysis presented in the next section we will show that excluding this
333 control has no effects on the results).

334 4 Results

335 4.1 Main Analysis

336 We start by verifying that, after the reform implementation, participants had not self-
337 selected through migration into one of the treatment branches. To do so, we collected data
338 regarding participants' village of origin, the number of years they have been living in the
339 village, and the eventual reason leading to migration. The vast majority of participants
340 reside in the same village where they were born (69% in treated and 72% in control,
341 χ^2 test $p > 10\%$). The majority of migrations were reported by female participants, and
342 marriage is the reason commonly declared for the move. The likelihood of having migrated
343 is the same across treatment branches. Finally, we verified that there is no statistically
344 significant difference across treatments between the fraction of adult life a participant had
345 spent in the village where she took part to the data collection (t-test two sided, $p > 10\%$).

¹⁵In the pre-analysis plan, we mentioned that “[S]ince our hypothesis specifies a clear prior regarding the direction of the reform effects, we will apply one-sided tests”. Pre-registering that we have theoretical reasons to use a one-sided test would make sense if we are implementing a z test for proportions. However, in the same passage we also mentioned that we would use a Chi-squared test, which is essentially a one-sided test (the use of the test as two-sided might generate a fit that is too good, as for instance in the controversy related to the famous Mendel’s pea experiments). In practice, the two-tail probability beyond $\pm z$ for the standard normal distribution equals the right-tail probability above z -squared for the chi-squared distribution with $df=1$ (Agresti, 2018, p.11). For completeness, we report both the results of a one-sided z test and of a Chi-squared test.

(a) Fraction of Utilitarian Participants

(b) by Market Integration

(c) by Income

Figure 3: Utilitarian Participants Across Treatments and Conditions

346 We begin the analysis by proposing a raw comparison of how many participants
 347 report to prefer the two utilitarian options (i.e. sparing the larger number of lives) in
 348 villages interested by the land tenure reform and in control villages. Out of a balanced
 349 sample consisting of 288 participants for each treatment branch, we have 206 individuals
 350 displaying utilitarian choices in treated villages against 193 in control villages. A z-test
 351 and chi-squared test show that the difference is not statistically significant. However, a

Table 1: Utilitarian Participants

	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3	Model 4
treated	0.380** (0.167)	0.465** (0.200)	0.479** (0.199)	0.580** (0.230)
sparing-man		-1.545*** (0.270)	-1.559*** (0.272)	-1.490*** (0.255)
dland			0.240 (0.337)	0.188 (0.335)
Standard-Controls	Y	Y	Y	Y
Wealth-Controls	N	N	N	Y
Constant	0.923 (0.876)	2.214** (1.025)	2.189** (1.037)	2.511* (1.285)
N.obs.	576	576	576	576

Notes: Dependent variable: Utilitarian. Logit regression. Standard errors robust for clustering at the village level. Standard-Controls included in all regressions: age, gender, religion, marital status, number of family members, participation to household finance management, years of education, whether the village of participation is also the village of birth, years of residence in the village, self-reported weekly income, incentivized measure of risk preferences, village population, distance from paved roads, and whether the village is located in the South. Model 2 adds a dummy for whether the participant took action to spare one man and sacrifice a woman. Model 3 additionally controls for whether participants possess individual land rights; Model 4 adds Wealth-Controls for: hectares of land owned, whether the house has cement floor, whether the household possess either a radio or a television, a motorbike or car, whether in the household somebody holds a bank account or a credit card, whether the house has electricity, whether the house has running water, self-reported rank of socio-economic status within the village (1-10). Symbols ***, **, and * indicate significance at the 1%, 5% and 10% level, respectively.

352 closer look at the post-experimental survey reveals that, among the residents in treated
353 villages who took part to the data collection, 82 individuals did not own land parcels
354 that were included in the land tenure reform and so they have not experienced directly
355 the formalization of property rights. This could happen either because an individual
356 does not possess land at all or because she holds use-rights over land parcels that are
357 located outside of the administrative boundaries of the treated villages, thus in an area
358 not interested by the PFR, which applied exclusively to land parcels within the treated
359 village borders (Goldstein et al., 2018). If we exclude from the sample the 82 residents
360 in treated villages who could have not been affected by the reform, we are left with 154
361 individuals making utilitarian choices, a fraction significantly larger than in the control
362 (one-sided z test, $p=3\%$; Chi-squared test, $p=6\%$).

363 We test our hypothesis in a Logistic regression framework. The dummy *utilitarian*
364 — which is equal to 1 when in both the decisions described above a participant spares
365 the largest number of lives — is regressed on the treatment dummy and a set of socio-

366 demographic controls,¹⁶ clustering standard errors at the village level. Model 1 in Table
367 1 reports the results. The coefficient of the dummy *treated* is positive and statistically
368 significant at the conventional level, indicating that a larger fraction of villagers in the
369 treated sample is engaging in utilitarian choices. The marginal effects of the estimate
370 coefficient suggests that experiencing the reform increases the likelihood of choosing the
371 utilitarian option by roughly 7% .

372 We continue the analysis by verifying whether controlling for gender preferences over
373 the individuals to be spared affects the results. Indeed, we know from the results reported
374 by Awad et al. (2018) that there are cross-country and cross-cultural variations concerning
375 preferences for sparing men versus women. In our setting, to be classified as ‘utilitarian’, a
376 participant must spare the largest number of lives irrespective of whether the individuals
377 to be saved are 2 males (Vignette 1 in Figure 1a) or two women (Vignette 2 in Figure
378 1a). As specified in the pre-analysis plan and discussed in section 3.1, we account for
379 a participant’s gender preferences in the moral dilemma choice by recording data from
380 Vignette 3 in Figure 1c where participants choose to either sacrifice a male pedestrian
381 or swerve and consequently kill a woman. In model 2, we then insert as a control a
382 dummy equal to 1 for those participants who decide to take action in order to save the
383 man and sacrifice the woman pedestrian. The qualitative results do not change compared
384 to the basic specification. The point estimate of the treatment variable becomes larger,
385 suggesting that experience with the property rights reform increases the likelihood of
386 being classified as utilitarian by approximately 9%. In model 3 we further add as a
387 control the dummy *dland* equal to one for participants who took part to the survey but
388 who do not own land parcels that could have been affected by the PFR. This could
389 happen for various reasons, for example because all the land belonging to the household
390 is located outside the village borders — and so not included in the PFR — or because
391 the respondents’ household does not possess use-rights over parcels of land at all. The
392 coefficient remains qualitatively and quantitatively similar to the one presented above.

393 In the context of low-medium-income countries self-reported income might not always
394 be an appropriate proxy for individual wealth (Arrow et al., 2012, Moser and Felton,
395 2007). Therefore, in model 4 we additionally include as controls a set of nine proxies

¹⁶The controls include: age, gender, religion, marital status, number of family members, participation to household finance management, years of education, whether the village of participation is also the village of birth, years of residence in the village, self-reported weekly income, incentivized measure of risk preferences, village population, distance from paved roads, and whether the village is located in the South.

396 for individual wealth.¹⁷ The coefficient of the treatment variable remains significant at
397 the conventional level, and the point estimate substantially increases, indicating that
398 participants in villages interested by the reform are on average 10.5% more likely than
399 those in control villages to make utilitarian choices. In connection to this, we further
400 verify the robustness of our results with respect to the measures of individual wealth we
401 control for. In Table 5 in Appendix A, we re-estimate the specification presented in model
402 4 by proposing four different proxies of individual wealth. Results remain qualitatively
403 the same and quantitatively very similar to those reported in Table 1.

404 As discussed in Section 3.2, one potential problem for our empirical strategy is that
405 participants across treatment groups lack balance for some individual characteristics (age,
406 marital status, having running water at home, and marginally literacy) that tend to be
407 positively associated with individual affluence.¹⁸ We address these concerns by pointing
408 out as a preliminary consideration that among participants in our survey having access
409 to water at home and being married, older, or in general more affluent than the sam-
410 ple median do not increase the frequency of utilitarian choices (two-sided z-test for the
411 four comparisons, $p=.15$; $p=.78$; $p=.33$; $p=.85$, respectively). Notice also that younger
412 people who are over-represented in our control sample actually display *higher* level of
413 utilitarianism – albeit the difference is not statistically significant.

414 To mitigate residual concerns, we implement a machine learning tool to select the
415 appropriate controls to be included in the regression analysis. Specifically, we re-estimate
416 the models presented in Table 1 employing the Lasso post-double-selection approach
417 proposed by Belloni et al. (2014).¹⁹ This methodology has been proved useful to select
418 the controls to be included in a regression when accidental imbalances in the sample
419 occurs in a principled way (Belloni et al., 2017, Chernozhukov et al., 2018). Table 4 in
420 Appendix A reports the results. The coefficient of the treatment dummy is confirmed to
421 be significant at the conventional level both in the base model specification (model 1) and
422 when we additionally account for participants in treated villages who does not possess
423 land (model 2). The magnitude of the estimated effect is similar to the one reported in

¹⁷The wealth controls include: hectares of land owned, whether the house has cement floor, whether the household possess either a radio or a television, a motorbike or car, whether in the household somebody holds a bank account or a credit card, whether the house has electricity, whether the house has running water, the self-reported rank of socio-economic status within the village (1-10).

¹⁸However, notice that in our sample participants older than the median age report on average lower – albeit not statistically different – income levels compared to younger participants.

¹⁹We additionally replicated the results discussed here by using the Lasso post-regularization methodology proposed by Chernozhukov et al. (2015) and developed as STATA package by Ahrens et al. (2018). Results are virtually identical.

424 the main analysis, thus adding confidence that the estimated increase in utilitarianism in
 425 villages where the reform was implemented is not driven by self-selection of more affluent
 426 individuals into the treated group. In section 4.2 we provide additional evidence related
 427 to this point.

428 Finally, the land demarcation and property rights registration process involved in the
 429 reform might have affected the rate of conflicts experienced by participants, and this
 430 in turn might have affected the moral preferences of the community. Participants in
 431 treated villages reported a total of 28 conflict episodes in the period following the re-
 432 form, a marginally larger number than the 14 episodes reported in the control group. We
 433 re-estimate the regression models presented in Table 1 adding a control for conflicts expe-
 434 rienced and we report results in Table 6 in Appendix A. The results remain qualitatively
 435 unchanged and point estimates very similar.

436 4.2 Heterogeneity Analysis

Table 2: Utilitarian Choices - Heterogeneity Analysis

	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3	Model 4	Model 5	Model 6
	Road Distance		Market Integration		Income	
Sample:	High	Low	High	Low	High	Low
treated	0.452 (0.331)	0.814*** (0.299)	1.368*** (0.432)	-0.135 (0.280)	0.820*** (0.313)	0.089 (0.277)
spare-man	-2.051*** (0.406)	-1.248*** (0.413)	-0.556 (0.444)	-2.186*** (0.330)	-1.600*** (0.341)	-1.552*** (0.375)
dland	-0.002 (0.022)	0.039 (0.036)	0.065 (0.044)	0.001 (0.025)	0.012 (0.014)	-0.007 (0.018)
Controls	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y
Constant	1.858** (0.795)	0.903 (1.256)	3.080** (1.300)	1.472 (1.376)	0.630 (0.870)	2.286* (1.309)
N.obs.	270	306	188	388	288	288

Notes: Dependent variable: Utilitarian. Logit regression. Standard errors robust for clustering at the village level. Controls included in all regressions: age, gender, religion, marital status, number of family members, participation to household finance management, years of education, whether the village of participation is also the village of birth, years of residence in the village, self-reported weekly income, incentivized measure of risk preferences, village population, distance from paved roads, and whether the village is located in the South. Models 1, 3, and 5 include only the participants living closer to paved road than the sample median, purchasing more than half of the total calorie intake on the market, and reporting a level of income higher than the sample median, respectively. Models 2, 4, and 6 include only the participants not included in Models 1, 2, 5. Symbols ***, **, and * indicate significance at the 1%, 5% and 10% level, respectively.

437 We then perform an heterogeneity analysis with respect to a set of villagers' socio-
438 demographic characteristics that could shed some light on the channels through which
439 formalized property rights affect moral preferences. We know from previous research
440 (Asher et al., 2018, Banerjee et al., 2020, Casaburi et al., 2013, Fabbri, 2020b) and from
441 the survey evidence discussed above that roads access is an important determinant of
442 the possibility to reach government institutions and state tribunals — thus to effectively
443 enforce the formalized property rights assigned by the reform. As a first step, we divide
444 subjects in two categories according to the distance of their village from the closest paved
445 roads. We consider only the sub-sample of 270 participants living in villages more distant
446 than the sample median to paved roads. We estimate for this subsample of participants
447 the specifications presented in model 4 of Table 1 We then repeat the comparison for
448 the subsample of 306 participants living at or closer than the sample median distance to
449 paved roads. Results are reported in models 1 and 2 of Table 2, respectively.

450 In model 1 the coefficient of the treatment variable becomes statistically not different
451 from zero. This suggests that, in our subsample of subjects living farther away from
452 paved road, the effect of experiencing the reform on developing utilitarian preferences
453 is negligible. Conversely, in model 2 the coefficient of the treatment dummy is strongly
454 statistically significant for the subsample of subjects living close to paved roads. The
455 point estimate suggests an increase of roughly 16% in the likelihood of making utilitarian
456 choices for treated individuals compared to control ones. Notice that the result reported
457 in model 2 cannot be driven by higher affluence of participants in the treated group,
458 since we are comparing a sample of participants reporting similar levels of income in
459 the treated and control samples – if anything, participants in control report on average
460 higher income than those in treated (CFA 8,800 vs. 6,800, respectively; $p > 10\%$, t-test
461 two-sided).

462 We continue the analysis by verifying whether two additional interrelated characteris-
463 tics, market integration and income levels, interact with the effects of the property rights
464 reform on moral preferences.²⁰ As a proxy for the level of market integration, we collected
465 data on the share of calories coming from self-produced products versus food purchased
466 on the market of a given household. We then classify as highly-market-integrated those
467 participants who report to purchase more than half of their total calories intake on the
468 market. In models 3 and 4 we isolate the effects of experiencing the reform on utilitarian

²⁰One reason why markets and income levels can interact with property in shaping moral preferences is that access to formal courts is costly and hence enforcement of property rights is *de facto* only available to higher-income individuals.

469 choices for the subsamples of participants characterized by high and low levels of market
470 integration, respectively. In the high-market-integration subsample, the formalization of
471 property rights significantly and substantially increases utilitarianism. The point esti-
472 mate suggests an increase of about 19% for treated participants in the likelihood of being
473 classified as utilitarian compared to control ones. Notice that also in this instance the
474 estimated difference in utilitarian choices cannot be due to differences in income, since
475 we are comparing a subsample of treated and control participants with roughly the same
476 income level (CFA 10,000 vs. 9,200 respectively, $p > 10\%$ t-test two-sided). Conversely,
477 in the low-market-integration subsample the estimated effect of the reform on utilitarian
478 morality is zero.

479 The heterogeneity analysis with respect to income levels points to a similar story. In
480 model 5, which isolates the effects of the reform on participants characterized by income
481 levels above the sample median, the coefficient of the treatment dummy is positive and
482 strongly statistically significant, suggesting an estimated 16% increase in the likelihood of
483 making utilitarian choices for participants experiencing formalized property rights. Once
484 more, by construction here we are comparing a subsample of participants characterized
485 by virtually the same income levels between treatment groups (CFA 16,100 for treated vs.
486 15,300 for control, $p > 10\%$ t-test two-sided), thus suggesting that the difference in the lev-
487 els of individualism observed across the two groups in this subsample does not depend on
488 participants' affluence. Conversely, the estimated effect is statistically indistinguishable
489 from zero for subjects in the low-income subsample, as shown by the coefficient estimate
490 of model 6.

491 5 Discussion

492 Our results raise several important questions as to their rationalization and implications,
493 which we address in this section.

494 5.1 A conjectural channel: the loosening of social ties

495 A natural question to ask is through which channel private property fosters utilitarianism.
496 Here we propose a conjecture: Formal property rights protected by state courts loosen the
497 web of social ties that support the allocation and enforcement of customary rights; in turn,
498 individuals are freed from the need to refrain from socially-alienating moral positions,
499 such as utilitarianism. The link between small communities with strong social ties and

500 their ability to operate internal rules of enforcement and conflict resolution outside and
501 sometime even in opposition to formal legal systems has been well documented in several
502 settings (Ellickson, 1991, Bernstein, 1992) and carries with it the opposite implication,
503 that close social ties can be detrimental to the development of impersonal institutions
504 (Greif, 1994, Greif and Tabellini, 2017). Here we add a twist to this line of argumentation
505 by suggesting that the introduction of impartial institutions can make social ties less
506 relevant and, as a result, loosen their grip on individuals' moral standings.

507 To start with, replies to the post-experimental survey by our participants show that
508 the reform resulted in an important increase in material security. We summarize the
509 relevant survey questions and responses in Table 7 in Appendix A. The vast majority
510 of individuals in treated villages appreciate the importance of the reform as protecting
511 rights on land through a system of record-keeping and adjudication in formal courts.
512 Importantly, villagers demonstrate to be well aware of the existence and function of
513 the newly established PFR registries, including their physical location, the possibility to
514 consult them, and their importance as evidence in case of conflicts. Roughly half of the
515 participants have in fact consulted the registry or know somebody who has. Respondents
516 reported to believe that the court system affords effective protection even in the event
517 of a conflict with a more powerful or wealthier individual, suggesting that the reform
518 provided tools for a more effective protection of property rights.

519 Consistent with this argument, we find that survey responses varied depending on
520 the distance from the closest paved road, a key determinant of effective access to the
521 formal legal system (Fabbri, 2020b). Individuals in villages closer to paved roads —
522 that is, closer than the median distance — face substantially lower costs of access to
523 formal courts (with a ratio of 1 to 3), and reported to have already had the experience
524 of resolving a land-related dispute in a formal court more often when compared to those
525 farther away. Indeed, easier access to paved roads is associated with substantially more
526 positive responses to the reform along most of the dimensions indicated above. Moreover,
527 individuals closer to paved roads reported a more diffused belief that decisions by formal
528 courts overrule those by customary courts, that disputes should be adjudicated before
529 formal courts rather than before customary courts, and that formal courts are less corrupt
530 than customary courts, as compared to the beliefs held by individuals farther away from
531 paved roads.

532 Overall, responses to the survey evidence a shared belief that the reform increased
533 material security for those with effective access to formal courts. It has been argued that
534 the lack of material security is a key factor contributing to an individual's parochial-

535 ism, that is, his or her tendency to favor a close circle of family, kin or friends over
536 strangers (Hruschka and Henrich, 2013). In turn, an improvement in material security
537 of the kind we discuss above is thought to encourage interactions with strangers outside
538 one’s own kith-and-kin community and the expansion of social networks. Indeed, exper-
539 imental results by one of us (Fabbri, 2020a) document increased levels of cooperation
540 with anonymous strangers belonging to other village communities for individuals who
541 experienced the PFR reform.

542 The next step in our conjecture is to link the loosening of social ties to an increase
543 in utilitarianism. Awad et al. (2020) argue that utilitarianism is related to relational-
544 mobility, that is, the independent position of an individual vis-a-vis the social network
545 in which he or she lives and operates. Using the Moral Machine platform, they collected
546 the responses of 70.000 subjects in 42 countries to three versions of the classic trolley
547 problem.²¹ They find variation across societies in the acceptability of utilitarian sacrifice
548 and document an association with “relational mobility”. In societies where individuals
549 have few opportunities to make new connections and break loose from their original
550 social network, it may be more important to refrain from holding opinions that could
551 potentially alienate friends. Holding a permissive moral position as to the acceptability
552 of utilitarian sacrifice may be considered as a signal of lack of trustworthiness and hence
553 have negative social consequences. As a result, condemnation of utilitarian sacrifice is the
554 more important the more valuable stable social ties are. In this view, morality is deeply
555 “socially functional” (Haidt, 2007) and hence is sensitive to the institutional setup of
556 society.

557 Other studies also support this point. Schulz et al. (2019) show that church policy
558 banning cousin marriage in the middle ages broke kinship ties, and that kinship ties
559 are negatively related to individualism, which, in turn is shown to be correlated with
560 utilitarian choices (Awad et al., 2018). This suggests that policies that loosen kinship ties
561 tend to result in more individualistic (and possibly utilitarian) attitudes. Similarly, Enke
562 (2019) shows that societies with historically loose kinship ties evolved moral attitudes —

²¹Subjects were asked whether it was morally acceptable to kill one in order to spare five in three different scenarios. In the *Switch* scenario a trolley is heading towards five workers and can be stopped by activating a switch that sends the trolley on a side track, away from the five but en route to one person who will consequently die. In the *Loop* scenario the side track is a loop and the killing of the one is instrumental in saving the five: his body will stop the trolley. Finally, in the *Footbridge* scenario, to save the five a large man must be pushed in front of the trolley. They find a universal qualitative ranking of the acceptability of utilitarian sacrifice in these three scenarios: Switch is more acceptable than Loop, which is more acceptable than Footbridge. They also found, however, quantitative variation as illustrated in the text.

563 universal moral values, internalized guilt and altruistic punishment — that are different
564 from those typical of societies with strong kinship ties.

565 While we stress that this is only a conjecture, we note that the evidence we collected
566 and a broad strand of literature seem to align well with the view that the formalization
567 of property rights resulted in increased utilitarianism through a change in how strongly
568 individuals relate to (and rely on) social connections within their local community.

569 **5.2 (In)commensurability**

570 Comparing values — such as when choosing between 1 lost life and 2 lost lives — gen-
571 erates a moral dilemma mainly because fundamental values are difficult to compare.
572 Philosophers have pointed to incommensurability as an obstacle to utilitarian choices
573 (Raz, 1988, Chang, 1997). Markets, in contrast, are grounded in the idea that the
574 goods traded can be compared by means of a common medium, money, and carry with
575 them a psychology of commensurability (Schwartz, 1986).

576 The property rights reform we study in this paper may be thought as having trans-
577 formed a resource — the access to which was regulated through a complex system of
578 social control accounting for family needs and redistribution — into a commodity that
579 can be freely traded on the market, and hence has an easily-recoverable monetary value.
580 Because land is one of the — if not the — most important productive asset in rural
581 Benin, the reform may have changed the way individuals regard not only land ownership
582 but “things of value” more generally, making value comparisons easier or more natural
583 and, in turn, utilitarian judgments more acceptable.

584 Indeed, the effects we measure are more pronounced in individuals who are more
585 reliant on markets. These considerations suggest an additional vector of moral change,
586 which is based on the individuals’ psychology and their relationship with goods and
587 values. This channel is consistent — and possibly concurrent — with the loosening of
588 social ties discussed above, which instead focuses on how individuals relate to each other.

589 **5.3 Co-evolution**

590 A large literature has emerged in economics around the idea that morality — or, more
591 generally, preferences — and institutions co-evolve (Bisin and Verdier, 2011, Mueller,
592 2018). While we only document one side of this relationship and, namely, that formal
593 institutions affect morality, others have emphasized the reverse effect, that of morality
594 on institutions.

595 Greif (1994) contrasts the close-kin relationship of the Maghribi traders and the more
596 individualistic attitudes of the Genovese traders. While close-kin relationships provided a
597 short-term advantage in terms of enforcement of claims, they also impaired the formation
598 of third-party enforcement systems which eventually favored the Genevose. Enke (2019)
599 emphasizes that the relationship between morality, kinship structure and economic out-
600 comes amplified over time because societies with loose kinship structures developed moral
601 attitudes that facilitated economic development, which in turn furthered the loosening of
602 social ties.

603 With respect to private property in particular, two studies (Lehavi and Licht, 2011,
604 Dari-Mattiacci and Guerriero, 2015) found that an individualistic culture tends to re-
605 sult in stronger property rights. A particular characteristic of the language spoken by
606 the plurality group — licence to drop the first-person pronoun in a sentence — is used
607 as an instrument for individualism.²² Since languages evolved before the formalization
608 of property rights, these studies conclude that culture affects the structure of property
609 rights. Given the cross-country correlation between a utilitarian morality and an indi-
610 vidualistic culture (Awad et al., 2018), their and our results suggest that there may be
611 a self-reinforcing co-evolutionary process of utilitarian moral attitudes and formal prop-
612 erty rights. Finally, these findings are in line with recent accounts of the institutional,
613 psychological and moral peculiarities of western populations (Henrich, 2020).

614 **5.4 Positive and negative utilitarianism**

615 Utilitarianism entails the maximization of aggregate welfare. The implication is that, if
616 to maximize aggregate welfare some harm must be done, which is less than the aggregate
617 gain, then that harm is permissible. A purely utilitarian calculus is unconstrained, that
618 is, it admits the production of *any* amount of harm as long as there is a corresponding
619 offsetting benefit that balances it. In contrast, deontological moral principles identify
620 harms that are inadmissible no matter the benefit. In this paper, we focus on this spe-
621 cific implication of utilitarianism, that is, individuals' acceptance of utilitarian sacrifice.
622 However, utilitarianism, as a normative ethical theory, is richer than that, which raises
623 the question whether one can extrapolate from an individual's acceptance of utilitarian
624 sacrifice to infer his or her adherence to the broader prescriptions of the theory. The
625 answer is most likely negative.

²²Languages that do not allow dropping the first-person pronoun (such as English) put more emphasis on the individual than languages (such as Italian) where pronoun-drop is allowed, which in turn correlates with survey measures of individualism.

626 Kahane et al. (2018) distinguishes between the general principle of welfare maximiza-
627 tion, or the doing of good, which is termed “positive utilitarianism”, and its “negative”
628 side, which is related to the production of harm. Put differently, the positive side of
629 utilitarianism embeds a form of moral altruism, where the moral imperative is to ac-
630 cept a personal loss if that allows for the creation of a greater good for somebody else.
631 In contrast, the negative side of utilitarianism embeds the absence or overcoming of
632 deontological constraints to the production of harm for others whenever that harm is
633 instrumental to the generation of a greater good. Kahane et al. (2018) emphasizes that
634 the positive and negative sides of utilitarianism are both philosophically and empirically
635 distinguished, and that moral dilemmas, such as the trolley problems used in this study,
636 are designed to exclusively capture the negative side (acceptability of harm) and carry
637 no weight for the positive counterpart (altruism). Consistently with this approach, in
638 a companion paper (Fabbri and Dari-Mattiacci, 2020), reporting on a previous wave of
639 incentivized experiments in different Beninese villages, we found that the reform had no
640 effect on individuals’ altruism.

641 **6 Conclusions**

642 In this paper we have showed that the randomized introduction of formal property rights
643 in a pool of Beninese villages resulted in a measurable moral drift towards utilitarianism.
644 Since formal property rights are a key feature of Western economies, our results relate
645 to recent studies on the moral and psychological peculiarities of Westerners (Henrich,
646 2020), and may contribute a factor explaining the the patterns of geographical variation
647 in moral attitudes across the globe (Awad et al., 2018). While our results focus on land,
648 the past several decades have seen an expansion of property rights in (and property-
649 rights narratives concerning) intangible assets, such as data and ideas. To the extent
650 that the effects we document are common to other forms of property, these trends may
651 be contributing to the factors pushing western societies towards becoming even more
652 utilitarian, as documented by Hannikainen et al. (2018). In addition, since property
653 rights reforms have been popular over the past few decades, our results imply that they
654 may have also set the reforms recipients on a path of changing moral values.

655 Our results may also have implications as to the effects of unintended institutional
656 changes. One of the largest and most cataclysmic events in recent history is the fall of
657 communism in the late 80s and early 90s and the demise of the USSR. Alesina and Fuchs-
658 Schündeln (2007) show that living under communism for 50 years in East Germany made

659 individuals believe more strongly that social conditions determine one's fortunes and favor
660 state intervention as compared to the control group of comparable West Germans. They
661 also show that preferences are quickly (re-)converging so that the two groups are predicted
662 to be indistinguishable within 2 generations. One could take the opposite perspective and
663 investigate the effect that the fall (rather than the introduction) of communism had on
664 preferences (and morality). Conspicuously, former communist countries reverted back to
665 formal private property. Our results suggest that morality may have changed in former
666 communist countries after the demise of communism in the same way as it changed in
667 rural Beninese villages.

668 The effect of property on utilitarianism that we document was measured only 9 years
669 after the reform. This is a remarkably short period of time if compared with the notion
670 of an innate psychology of ownership acquired in early childhood (Nancekivell et al.,
671 2019) and with studies evidencing that moral change in society occurs especially across-
672 generations, with limited effect within-generations (Hannikainen et al., 2018). What
673 explains the short-term effects we detect? Is the long-term impact of the reform even
674 larger or are its full effects already tangible? While we offer a conjecture as to the channels
675 through which formal property affects morality, more research is needed in order to clarify
676 the psychological and sociological mechanisms at work.

677 **References**

- 678 Abarbanell, L. and Hauser, M. D. (2010). Mayan morality: An exploration of permissible
679 harms. *Cognition*, 115(2):207–224.
- 680 Agresti, A. (2018). *An introduction to categorical data analysis*. John Wiley & Sons.
- 681 Ahrens, A., Hansen, C. B., and Schaffer, M. E. (2018). *pdlasso and ivlasso: Programs*
682 *for post-selection and post-regularization ols or iv estimation and inference*. Technical
683 report, Statistical Software Components, Boston College Department of Economics.
- 684 Alesina, A. and Fuchs-Schündeln, N. (2007). Good-Bye Lenin (or Not?): The Effect of
685 Communism on People's Preferences. *American Economic Review*, 97(4):1507–1528.
- 686 Alesina, A. and Giuliano, P. (2015). Culture and Institutions. *Journal of Economic*
687 *Literature*, 53(4):898–944.

- 688 André, C. and Platteau, J. P. (1998). Land relations under unbearable stress: Rwanda
689 caught in the Malthusian trap. *Journal of Economic Behavior and Organization*,
690 34(1):1–47.
- 691 Arrow, K. J., Dasgupta, P., Goulder, L. H., Mumford, K. J., and Oleson, K. (2012). Sus-
692 tainability and the measurement of wealth. *Environment and development economics*,
693 17(3):317–353.
- 694 Asher, S., Nagpal, K., and Novosad, P. (2018). The cost of distance: Geography and
695 governance in rural india. *World Bank Working Paper*.
- 696 Awad, E., Dsouza, S., Kim, R., Schulz, J., Henrich, J., Shariff, A., Bonnefon, J.-F., and
697 Rahwan, I. (2018). The moral machine experiment. *Nature*, 563(7729):59–64.
- 698 Awad, E., Dsouza, S., Shariff, A., Rahwan, I., and Bonnefon, J.-F. (2020). Universals and
699 variations in moral decisions made in 42 countries by 70,000 participants. *Proceedings*
700 *of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America*, 117(5):2332–2337.
- 701 Banerjee, A., Duflo, E., and Qian, N. (2020). On the road: Access to transportation
702 infrastructure and economic growth in china. *Journal of Development Economics*,
703 145:102442.
- 704 Becker, A., Enke, B., and Falk, A. (2020). Ancient Origins of the Global Variation in
705 Economic Preferences. *AEA Papers and Proceedings*, 110:319–323.
- 706 Belloni, A., Chernozhukov, V., Fernández-Val, I., and Hansen, C. (2017). Program eval-
707 uation and causal inference with high-dimensional data. *Econometrica*, 85(1):233–298.
- 708 Belloni, A., Chernozhukov, V., and Hansen, C. (2014). Inference on treatment effects
709 after selection among high-dimensional controls. *The Review of Economic Studies*,
710 81(2):608–650.
- 711 Bentham, J. (1789 [1907]). An introduction to the principles of morals and legislation.
- 712 Bernstein, L. (1992). Opting out of the Legal System: Extralegal Contractual Relations
713 in the Diamond Industry. *The Journal of Legal Studies*, 21(1):115–157.
- 714 Bisin, A. and Verdier, T. (2011). The economics of cultural transmission and socialization.
715 In Benhabib, J., Bisin, A., and Jackson, M. O., editors, *Handbook of Social Economics*.
716 *Vol. 1*, pages 339–416. Elsevier, Amsterdam.

- 717 Bowles, S. (1998). Endogenous Preferences: The Cultural Consequences of Markets and
718 other Economic Institutions. *Journal of Economic Literature*, 36(1):75–111.
- 719 Casaburi, L., Glennerster, R., and Suri, T. (2013). Rural roads and intermediated trade:
720 Regression discontinuity evidence from sierra leone. *Available at SSRN 2161643*.
- 721 Chang, R. e. (1997). *Incommensurability, incomparability, and practical reason*. Harvard
722 University Press.
- 723 Chernozhukov, V., Demirer, M., Duflo, E., and Fernandez-Val, I. (2018). Generic ma-
724 chine learning inference on heterogenous treatment effects in randomized experiments.
725 Technical report, National Bureau of Economic Research.
- 726 Chernozhukov, V., Hansen, C., and Spindler, M. (2015). Post-selection and post-
727 regularization inference in linear models with many controls and instruments. *American*
728 *Economic Review*, 105(5):486–90.
- 729 Christensen, J. and Gomila, A. (2012). Moral dilemmas in cognitive neuroscience of
730 moral decision-making: A principled review. *Neuroscience & Biobehavioral Reviews*,
731 36(4):1249–1264.
- 732 Dagan, H. and Dorfman, A. (2016). Just Relationships. *Columbia Law Review*,
733 116(6):1395–1460.
- 734 Dari-Mattiacci, G. and Guerriero, C. (2015). Law and culture: A theory of comparative
735 variation in bona fide purchase rules. *Oxford Journal of Legal Studies*, 35(3):543–574.
- 736 Deininger, K. and Castagnini, R. (2006). Incidence and impact of land conflict in uganda.
737 *Journal of Economic Behavior & Organization*, 60(3):321–345.
- 738 Delville, P. et al. (2000). Harmonising formal law and customary land rights in french-
739 speaking west africa. *Evolving land rights, policy and tenure in Africa.*, pages 97–122.
- 740 Di Tella, R., Galiani, S., and Schargrodsy, E. (2007). The Formation of Beliefs: Evidence
741 from the Allocation of Land Titles to Squatters. *The Quarterly Journal of Economics*,
742 122(1):209–241.
- 743 Elias, N. (2000). *The civilizing process: sociogenetic and psychogenetic investigations*.
744 Blackwell, Hoboken, NJ, 2nd edition.

- 745 Ellickson, R. C. (1991). *Order Without Law: How Neighbors Settle Disputes*. Harvard
746 University Press, Cambridge, MA.
- 747 Enke, B. (2019). Kinship, cooperation, and the evolution of moral systems. *Quarterly*
748 *Journal of Economics*, 134(2):953–1019.
- 749 Enke, B. (2020). Moral Values and Voting. *Journal of Political Economy*, 128(10):3679–
750 3729.
- 751 Fabbri, M. (2020a). Institutional Quality Shapes Cooperation with Out-group Strangers.
752 *mimeo*.
- 753 Fabbri, M. (2020b). Property Rights and Prosocial Behavior: Evidence from a Land
754 Tenure Reform Implemented as Randomized Control-Trial. *mimeo*.
- 755 Fabbri, M. and Dari-Mattiacci, G. (2020). The virtuous cycle of property. *Review of*
756 *Economics and Statistics*.
- 757 Falk, A. and Szech, N. (2013). Morals and Markets. *Science*, 340(6133):707–711.
- 758 Foot, P. (1967). The Problem of Abortion and the Doctrine of the Double Effect. *Oxford*
759 *Review*, 5:5–15.
- 760 Foucault, M. (1995). *Discipline and punish: the birth of the prison*. Vintage Books, New
761 York, NY.
- 762 Garnsey, P. (2014). *Thinking about Property: From Antiquity to the Age of Revolution*.
763 Ideas in Context. Cambridge University Press.
- 764 Goldstein, M., Hounbedji, K., Kondylis, F., O’Sullivan, M., and Selod, H. (2016). For-
765 malizing rural land rights in west africa: Early evidence from a randomized impact
766 evaluation in benin. *World Bank Policy Research Working Paper*, (7435).
- 767 Goldstein, M., Hounbedji, K., Kondylis, F., O’Sullivan, M., and Selod, H. (2018). For-
768 malization without certification? experimental evidence on property rights and invest-
769 ment. *Journal of Development Economics*, 132:57–74.
- 770 Greene, J. D. (2016). Solving the Trolley Problem. In Sytsma, J. and Buckwalter, W.,
771 editors, *A Companion to Experimental Philosophy*, pages 173–189. John Wiley & Sons,
772 Ltd, Chichester, UK.

- 773 Greif, A. (1994). Cultural Beliefs and the Organization of Society: A Historical and
774 Theoretical Reflection on Collectivist and Individualist Societies. *Journal of Political*
775 *Economy*, 102(5):912–950.
- 776 Greif, A. and Tabellini, G. (2017). The clan and the corporation: Sustaining cooperation
777 in China and Europe. *Journal of Comparative Economics*, 45(1):1–35.
- 778 Haidt, J. (2007). The New Synthesis in Moral Psychology. *Science*, 316(5827):998 LP –
779 1002.
- 780 Haidt, J. and Graham, J. (2007). When Morality Opposes Justice: Conservatives Have
781 Moral Intuitions that Liberals may not Recognize. *Social Justice Research*, 20(1):98–
782 116.
- 783 Hannikainen, I. R., Machery, E., and Cushman, F. A. (2018). Is utilitarian sacrifice
784 becoming more morally permissible? *Cognition*, 170:95–101.
- 785 Henrich, J. (2020). *The WEIRDest People in the World: How the West Became Psycho-*
786 *logically Peculiar and Particularly Prosperous*. Farrar, Straus and Giroux, New York,
787 NY.
- 788 Henrich, J., Boyd, R., Bowles, S., Camerer, C., Fehr, E., Gintis, H., and McElreath, R.
789 (2001). In Search of Homo Economicus: Behavioral Experiments in 15 Small-Scale
790 Societies. *American Economic Review*, 91(2):73–78.
- 791 Henrich, J., Boyd, R., Bowles, S., Camerer, C., Fehr, E., Gintis, H., McElreath, R.,
792 Alvard, M., Barr, A., Ensminger, J., et al. (2005). „Économic man,À in cross-
793 cultural perspective: Behavioral experiments in 15 small-scale societies. *Behavioral*
794 *and brain sciences*, 28(6):795–815.
- 795 Hounkpodote, R. (2007). Manuel de procédures pour l,Àétablissement du plan foncier
796 rural. *Cellule opérationnelle Plan foncier rural, MCA-Bénin/GTZ*.
- 797 Hruschka, D. J. and Henrich, J. (2013). Economic and evolutionary hypotheses for cross-
798 population variation in parochialism. *Frontiers in human neuroscience*, 7:559.
- 799 Jha, S. and Shayo, M. (2019). Valuing Peace: The Effects of Financial Market Exposure
800 on Votes and Political Attitudes. *Econometrica*, 87(5):1561–1588.
- 801 John Paul II (1995). *Evangelium vitae*. Papal encyclical.

- 802 Kahane, G., Everett, J. A. C., Earp, B. D., Caviola, L., Faber, N. S., Crockett, M. J., and
803 Savulescu, J. (2018). Beyond sacrificial harm: A two-dimensional model of utilitarian
804 psychology. *Psychological review*, 125(2):131–164.
- 805 Kamm, F. M. (1989). Harming some to save others. *Philosophical Studies*, 57(3):227–260.
- 806 Kaplow, L. and Shavell, S. (2001). Fairness Versus Welfare. *Harvard Law Review*, 114:961–
807 1388.
- 808 Lehavi, A. and Licht, A. N. (2011). BITs and Pieces of Property. *Yale Journal of*
809 *International Law*, 36(1):115–166.
- 810 Lowes, S., Nunn, N., Robinson, J. A., and Weigel, J. L. (2017). The Evolution of Culture
811 and Institutions: Evidence From the Kuba Kingdom. *Econometrica*, 85(4):1065–1091.
- 812 Margalit, Y. and Shayo, M. (2020). How Markets Shape Values and Political Preferences:
813 A Field Experiment. *American Journal of Political Science*, XX:XX–XX.
- 814 Merrill, T. and Smith, H. (2007). The Morality of Property. *William & Mary Law*
815 *Review*, 48:1849–1895.
- 816 Mill, J. S. (1863). *Utilitarianism*. Parker, Son, and Bourne, London.
- 817 Moser, C. and Felton, A. (2007). The construction of an asset index measuring asset
818 accumulation in ecuador. *Chronic poverty research centre working paper*, (87).
- 819 Mueller, B. (2018). The Coevolution of Institutions and Culture. In Menard, C. and
820 Shirley, M. M., editors, *A Research Agenda for New Institutional Economics*, pages
821 153–161. Edward Elgar, Cheltenham.
- 822 Nancekivell, S. E., Friedman, O., and Gelman, S. A. (2019). Ownership Matters: People
823 Possess a Naïve Theory of Ownership. *Trends in Cognitive Sciences*, 23(2):102–113.
- 824 Omondi, K. (2019). Mcc evaluation report - ie of access to land project in benin - final.
825 Technical report.
- 826 Posner, R. A. (1979). Utilitarianism, Economics, and Legal Theory. *The Journal of Legal*
827 *Studies*, 8(1):103–140.
- 828 Rawls, J. (1971). *A theory of justice*. Harvard University Press, Cambridge, MA.

- 829 Raz, J. (1988). *The Morality of Freedom*. Oxford University Press.
- 830 Schulz, J. F., Bahrami-Rad, D., Beauchamp, J. P., and Henrich, J. (2019). The Church,
831 intensive kinship, and global psychological variation. *Science*, 366(6466):1–12.
- 832 Schwartz, B. (1986). *Battle For Human Nature: Science, Morality And Modern Life*.
833 Norton, New York (NY).
- 834 Singer, P. (2011). *The expanding circle: Ethics, evolution, and moral progress*. Princeton
835 University Press, Princeton, NJ.
- 836 Smart, R. N. (1958). Negative utilitarianism. *Mind*, 67(268):542–543.
- 837 Tabellini, G. (2008a). Presidential Address. Institutions and Culture. *Journal of the*
838 *European Economic Association*, 6(2-3):255–294.
- 839 Tabellini, G. (2008b). The Scope of Cooperation: Values and Incentives. *Quarterly*
840 *Journal of Economics*, 123(3):905–950.
- 841 Thomson, J. J. (1976). Killing, Letting Die, and the Trolley Problem. *The Monist*,
842 59:204–217.
- 843 Thomson, J. J. (1984). The Trolley Problem. *Yale Law Journal*, 94(6):1395–1415.
- 844 Unger, P. (1996). *Living High and Letting Die*. Oxford University Press, Oxford.
- 845 Weber, E. (1976). *Peasants into Frenchmen: the modernization of rural France, 1870-*
846 *1914*. Stanford University Press, Stanford.
- 847 Zhang, T. (2016). Cultural Paradigms in Property Institutions. *Yale Journal of Interna-*
848 *tional Law*, 41(2):347–413.

849 **A Supplementary Analysis**

Table 3: Balance of Observables Across Treatment Groups (t test two-sided for continuous variable and Chi-square test for dummy variables)

	PFR Reform (n=288)	Control (n=288)	Difference (p-value)
male	.49	.51	.73
age	40.0	36.8	.01
muslim	.45	.41	.27
vodoun	.19	.18	.91
married	.89	.83	.02
householdnr	9.8	10.0	.68
managefinance	.95	.95	.99
literate	.40	.33	.08
bornvillage	.69	.72	.41
yearsinvillage	32.3	30.9	.24
weekly income (XOF)	9,026	8,468	.59
landuse (Hect)	5.47	5.10	.65
concretefloor	.64	.59	.23
electricity	.36	.36	.99
water	.26	.18	.02
radio-TV	.63	.63	.99
car	.09	.07	.28
moto	.77	.78	.69
bank-acc	.33	.27	.12
social-rank	4.45	4.36	.56

Figure 4: Utilitarian choices comparing across treatment groups participants with high income (left panel) and low income (right panel).

Table 4: Utilitarian Participants - Lasso Post-double-selection Methodology for Selection of Controls (Belloni et al., 2014)

	Model 1	Model 2
treated	0.076** (0.034)	0.078** (0.033)
managemoney	-0.228** (0.100)	-0.259*** (0.096)
literate	0.150*** (0.037)	0.146*** (0.036)
sparing-man	-0.332*** (0.050)	-0.333*** (0.050)
dist-road	0.004** (0.002)	0.004** (0.002)
south	-0.116*** (0.034)	-0.095** (0.040)
population	-0.000 (0.000)	-0.000 (0.000)
dland		0.058 (0.059)
Constant	0.935*** (0.114)	0.919*** (0.120)
N.obs.	576	576

Notes: Dependent variable: Utilitarian. Regularized post-double-selection lasso regression. Standard errors robust for clustering at the village level. High-dim controls included: age, gender, religion, marital status, number of family members, participation to household finance management, years of literate, whether the village of participation is also the village of birth, years of residence in the village, self-reported weekly income, incentivized measure of risk preferences. Models 2 includes as an additional unpenalized control whether participants possess individual land rights. Symbols ***, **, and * indicate significance at the 1%, 5% and 10% level, respectively.

Table 5: Utilitarian Participants - Different Wealth Measures

	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3	Model 4
treated	0.475** (0.196)	0.557** (0.231)	0.498** (0.212)	0.476** (0.206)
Constant	2.814** (1.266)	2.247** (1.086)	2.277* (1.183)	2.439** (1.165)
N.obs.	576	576	576	576

Notes: Dependent variable: Utilitarian. Logit regression. Standard errors robust for clustering at the village level. Controls included in all regressions: age, gender, religion, marital status, number of family members, participation to household finance management, years of education, whether the village of participation is also the village of birth, years of residence in the village, incentivized measure of risk preferences, village population, distance from paved roads, and whether the village is located in the South, a dummy for whether the participant took action to spare one man and sacrifice a woman. As a proxy for wealth, model 1 uses self-reported rank of socio-economic status within the village (1-10); model 2 hectares of land owned, whether the house has cement floor, whether the house has electricity, whether the house has running water; model 3 whether the household possess either a radio or a television, a motorbike or car, whether in the household somebody holds a bank account or a credit card; model 4 a compounded index of income (whether above or below the median) and all the elements in models 1-3. Symbols ***, **, and * indicate significance at the 1%, 5% and 10% level, respectively.

Table 6: Utilitarian Participants - Controlling for Conflicts Experienced

	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3	Model 4
treated	0.382** (0.168)	0.468** (0.201)	0.500** (0.198)	0.436** (0.197)
conflicts	-0.048 (0.322)	-0.085 (0.350)	0.001 (0.348)	0.053 (0.341)
sparing-man		-1.547*** (0.260)	-1.558*** (0.250)	-1.638*** (0.271)
dland			0.300 (0.334)	0.338 (0.331)
Wealth Controls	N	N	N	Y
Constant	1.044 (0.902)	2.329** (1.074)	2.771** (1.252)	3.280*** (1.210)
N.obs.	576	576	576	576

Notes: Dependent variable: Utilitarian. Logit regression. Standard errors robust for clustering at the village level. Controls included in all regressions: age, gender, religion, marital status, number of family members, participation to household finance management, years of education, whether the village of participation is also the village of birth, years of residence in the village, self-reported weekly income, incentivized measure of risk preferences, village population, distance from paved roads, and whether the village is located in the South. Model 2 adds a dummy for whether the participant took action to spare one man and sacrifice a woman. Model 3 additionally controls for whether participants possess individual land rights; Model 4 adds controls for: hectares of land owned, whether the house has cement floor, whether the household possess either a radio or a television, a motorbike or car, whether in the household somebody holds a bank account or a credit card, whether the house has electricity, whether the house has running water, self-reported rank of socio-economic status within the village (1-10). Symbols ***, **, and * indicate significance at the 1%, 5% and 10% level, respectively.

Table 7: Post-experimental Survey (Treated Villages Sample)

	Road distance		diff
	High	Low	
Importance of PFR			
1. Believes PFR certificate protects from expropriation	91%	94%	
2. Believes PFR certificate helps prevail in a conflict with powerful individual	89%	89%	
3. Willing to contest eviction due to PFR	44%	40%	
4. Would ask for PFR certificate before buying land	96%	97%	
Knowledge and beliefs about PFR			
5. Knows where to consult PFR registry	26%	37%	**
6. Knows somebody who consulted PFR	24%	39%	***
7. Thinks conflicts should be solved before formal court	15%	53%	***
8. Thinks formal court decisions are more important than customary court decisions	66%	88%	***
9. Thinks formal courts are more effective in resolving conflicts than customary courts (scale: 1-7)	3.36	3.76	***
10. Thinks that formal courts are as corrupt as or less corrupt than customary courts	20%	45%	***
11. Thinks formal courts can be used by the rich to subvert decisions taken by customary courts	86%	80%	
Experience with PFR			
12. Initiated procedure in formal courts rather than customary court	16%	40%	*
13. Knows somebody who solved a conflict in formal courts	9%	41%	***
14. Costs of conflict resolution before formal courts (thousand XOF)	1,233	382	**

Notes: For each question N=276, except for questions 12 and 14 where N=38 (these questions were posed only to respondents reporting to have had land-related conflicts). Symbols ***, **, and * indicate significance at the 1%, 5% and 10% level, respectively.

850 **B Additional Vignettes Presented During the Field-**
851 **work**

The car in the pictures below has sudden brake failure: What would you do if you were driving the car?
Choose one of the two options below.

CONTINUE STRAIGHT

In this case the car will drive through a pedestrian crossing ahead, which will result in the death of:
1 elderly man

SWERVE

In this case the car will drive through a pedestrian crossing in the other lane, which will result in the death of:
1 man

Figure 5: Vignette 4. One elderly men vs. one man

The car in the pictures below has sudden brake failure: What would you do if you were driving the car?
Choose one of the two options below.

CONTINUE STRAIGHT

In this case the car will drive through a pedestrian crossing ahead, which will result in the death of:
1 man

SWERVE

In this case the car will drive through a pedestrian crossing in the other lane, which will result in the death of:
1 boy

Figure 6: Vignette 5. One man vs. one boy

The car in the pictures below has sudden brake failure: What would you do if you were driving the car?
Choose one of the two options below.

CONTINUE STRAIGHT

In this case the car will drive through a pedestrian crossing ahead, which will result in the death of:
1 elderly man

SWERVE

In this case the car will drive through a pedestrian crossing in the other lane, which will result in the death of:
1 boy

Figure 7: Vignette 6. One elderly man vs. one boy

The car in the pictures below has sudden brake failure: What would you do if you were driving the car?
Choose one of the two options below.

CONTINUE STRAIGHT

In this case the car will drive through a pedestrian crossing ahead, which will result in the death of:
1 male executive

SWERVE

In this case the car will drive through a pedestrian crossing in the other lane, which will result in the death of:
1 man

Figure 8: Vignette 7. One male executive vs. one man

The car in the pictures below has sudden brake failure: What would you do if you were driving the car?
Choose one of the two options below.

CONTINUE STRAIGHT

In this case the car will drive through a pedestrian crossing ahead, which will result in the death of:
1 male doctor

SWERVE

In this case the car will drive through a pedestrian crossing in the other lane, which will result in the death of:
1 man

Figure 9: Vignette 8. One male doctor vs. one man

The car in the pictures below has sudden brake failure: What would you do if you were driving the car?
Choose one of the two options below.

CONTINUE STRAIGHT

In this case the car will drive through a pedestrian crossing ahead, which will result in the death of:
1 male executive

SWERVE

In this case the car will drive through a pedestrian crossing in the other lane, which will result in the death of:
1 male doctor

Figure 10: Vignette 9. One executive vs. one doctor